

Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Hydrolysis of Some (Substituted Salicylato) Pentaammine-Cobalt(III) Complexes

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Manuscript received 6 December 1975, revised 6 March 1976 ; accepted 11 March 1976

The acid hydrolysis of some pentaammine(substituted salicylato) cobalt(III) complexes has been studied spectrophotometrically in the temperature range 65°-80° in a medium of 1.0M ionic strength adjusted with NaClO₄.

Aquation of the complexes proceed by two parallel paths, one independent of [H⁺] and another first-order in [H⁺]. Rate constants and activation parameters for both the paths have been determined.

THE kinetics and mechanism of acid hydrolysis of some carboxylatopentaammine-Co(III) complexes have been investigated¹. Such reactions have generally been found to proceed by acid independent and acid dependent paths. It is known that the acid catalysed aquation of carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes involve either Co-O or C-O bond fission. The acid hydrolysis of salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) and 5-sulphosalicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes has been studied in this laboratory^{2,3}. In the present paper we report the kinetics of acid hydrolysis of some more substituted salicylato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes in order to know the effect of substituents on the uncatalysed and acid catalysed aquation paths of these substrates.

Experimental

Substituted salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorates, [(NH₃)₅CoCO₂C₆H₃(x)OH](ClO₄)₂, were prepared as described earlier⁴, purified by recrystallisation from aqueous perchloric acid solution and dried over fused calcium chloride at room temperature. Purity of each sample was checked by estimating the cobalt content. Spectral and analytical data for the complexes are given in Table 1.

The absorption spectra of the freshly prepared complexes solutions in the visible and ultraviolet regions were found to be independent of [H⁺] over the acidity range 0.05 to 1.0 M.

B. D. H. reagent grade sodium perchlorate (recrystallised) and E. Merck (G. R.) perchloric acid were used to adjust the ionic strength and the acidity of the reaction medium respectively. All other reagents used, were of B. D. H. (AR) quality. All solutions were prepared in distilled water. Optical density measurements were made with a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer using 1 cm. matched silica cells.

Kinetics

Requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid mixtures were thermostatted at the desired temperature. After thermal equilibrium was reached a known volume of the complex of concentration (1.9~2.1) × 10⁻⁴M was quickly transferred into the reaction flask. The volume was made up with distilled water previously equilibrated at the same temperature and shaken. Measured volume of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at definite time intervals and quickly transferred to previously dried

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA

Complex	% of cobalt		λ _{max} , nm	ε _{max} , m ⁻¹ , cm ⁻¹
	Calcd	Found		
[(NH ₃) ₅ CoCO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ (5-Br)OH](ClO ₄) ₂	10.5	10.4	510	82.7
[(NH ₃) ₅ CoCO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ (5-NO ₂)OH](ClO ₄) ₂	11.2	11.1	510	80.7
[(NH ₃) ₅ CoCO ₂ C ₆ H ₃ (3-NO ₂)OH](ClO ₄) ₂	11.2	10.9	510	88.5

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clean test tubes placed inside crushed ice in order to quench the reaction. Optical densities of such solutions were measured at preset wavelengths at room temperature.

A computer programme was adapted to the I. B. M. 1130 computer to calculate the observed rate constants from the least squares best slopes for the straight line

plots of $\ln(D_t - D_\infty)$ vs. t , where D_t and D_∞ stand for the optical densities of the reaction mixtures at time 't' and at infinite time respectively. D_∞ for any run was taken to be the measured optical density of a solution whose composition corresponded exactly to that for complete reaction for that run. The error quoted for the observed rate constants (Table 2, 3 and 4) were calculated from the least squares standard deviations of the slopes for such plots.

TABLE 2—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF $[(NH_3)_5CoOCOC_6H_5(5-BR)OH]^{2+}$ AT $\mu=1.0M$

[H ⁺],M	65.0(±0.1)°		70.0(±0.1)°		75.0(0.1)°	
	obs	calcd	obs	calcd	obs	calcd
0.05	1.82(±0.08)	1.85	3.88(±0.19)	4.72	11.5(±0.9)	7.75
0.1	2.40(±0.28)	2.41	6.11(±0.10)	5.73	13.3(±0.1)	10.56
0.2					18.8(±0.4)	16.17
0.3	4.23(±0.29)	4.62	8.90(±0.12)	9.42		
0.4					31.1(±0.2)	27.40
0.5	7.25(±0.28)	6.83	14.0(±0.2)	13.11		
0.6			14.6(±0.2)	14.95	40.7(±0.1)	38.61
0.8	10.5(±0.8)	10.15	17.6(±0.5)	18.64	48.6(±0.2)	49.84
1.0	12.4(±0.4)	12.37	22.1(±0.5)	22.33	60.9(±0.1)	61.09
10 ⁶ k ₀ , sec ⁻¹	1.30(±0.07)		3.10(±0.16)		8.49(±0.12)	
10 ⁶ k ₁ , M ⁻¹ , sec ⁻¹	11.1(±0.1)		18.4(±0.3)		52.4(±0.2)	

$\Delta H^*(k_0\text{path})=25.5(\pm 0.9)$ k, cal/mole, $\Delta S^*(k_0\text{path})=-9.6(\pm 2.7)$ e.u.
 $\Delta H^*(k_1\text{path})=38.4(\pm 0.2)$ k, cal/mole, $\Delta S^*(k_1\text{path})=32.1(\pm 0.6)$ e.u.

TABLE 3—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF $[(NH_3)_5CoOCOC_6H_5(5-NO_2)OH]^{2+}$ AT $\mu=1.0M$

[H ⁺],M	70.0(±0.1)°		75.1(±0.1)°		80.0(±0.1)°	
	obs	calcd	obs	calcd	obs	calcd
0.05	5.11(±0.09)	5.98	11.3(±0.1)	13.50	21.2(±0.1)	21.67
0.1	7.31(±0.10)	6.50	14.6(±0.2)	14.41	24.9(±0.2)	22.94
0.2	7.90(±0.07)	7.56	15.5(±0.1)	16.24	25.4(±0.2)	25.50
0.4	9.47(±0.07)	9.67	17.6(±0.3)	19.88	30.9(±0.4)	30.60
0.6	11.7(±0.1)	11.77	21.5(±0.1)	23.53	37.2(±0.2)	35.71
0.8	13.6(±0.4)	13.88	26.4(±0.1)	27.17	40.8(±0.1)	40.81
1.0	17.1(±0.2)	16.00	31.6(±0.3)	30.82	47.4(±0.4)	45.91
10 ⁶ k ₀ , sec ⁻¹	5.45(±0.06)		12.6(±0.1)		20.4(±0.1)	
10 ⁶ k ₁ , M ⁻¹ , sec ⁻¹	10.5(±0.1)		18.2(±0.1)		25.5(±0.1)	

$\Delta H^*(k_0\text{path})=29.8(\pm 0.3)$ k, cal/mole, $\Delta S^*=4.2(\pm 0.7)$ e.u.
 $\Delta H^*(k_1\text{path})=19.7(\pm 0.3)$ k, cal/mole, $\Delta S^*=-24(\pm 0.8)$ e.u.

TABLE 4—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR ACID HYDROLYSIS OF $[(NH_3)_5CoOCOC_6H_5(3-NO_2)OH]^{2+}$ AT $\mu=1.0M$

[H ⁺],M	70.0(±0.1)°		75(±0.1)°		80.0(±0.1)°	
	obs	calcd	obs	calcd	obs	calcd
0.05	6.45(±0.05)	6.44	13.2(±0.0)	13.36	25.8(±0.7)	28.06
0.1	7.60(±0.01)	7.46	15.9(±0.4)	14.94	29.0(±0.7)	30.35
0.2	9.25(±0.30)	9.49	17.5(±0.2)	18.10	34.0(±0.7)	34.92
0.4	14.3(±0.7)	13.55	23.8(±0.3)	24.43	45.1(±0.1)	44.05
0.6	17.6(±0.1)	17.61	31.0(±0.2)	30.75	54.7(±0.2)	53.18
0.8	19.1(±1.0)	21.67	36.7(±0.7)	37.08	61.3(±0.3)	62.32
1.0	26.0(±1.6)	25.73	42.9(±0.5)	43.40	72.5(±0.4)	71.32
10 ⁶ k ₀ , sec ⁻¹	5.43(±0.06)		11.8(±0.2)		25.8(±0.3)	
10 ⁶ k ₁ , M ⁻¹ , sec ⁻¹	20.3(±0.2)		31.6(±0.5)		45.7(±0.5)	

$\Delta H^*(k_0\text{path})=36.7(\pm 0.4)$ kcal/mole, $\Delta S^*(k_0\text{path})=24.2(\pm 1.2)$ e.u.
 $\Delta H^*(k_1\text{path})=18.9(\pm 0.4)$ kcal/mole, $\Delta S^*(k_1\text{path})=-25.2(\pm 1.1)$ e.u.

Results

The aquation of the substituted salicylatopentaamine cobalt(III) complexes were studied in perchloric acid solutions over the acidity range 0.05–0.1M at an ionic strength of 1.0M (adjusted with sodium perchlorate wherever necessary). The concentration of the complex varied from $(1.90\sim 2.1) \times 10^{-4}M$. The pseudo first order rate constants for the aquation reaction at different $[H^+]$ and over the temperature range $65^\circ - 80^\circ$ are given in Tables 2, 3 and 4.

Plots of k_{obs} vs. $[H^+]$ were found to be linear with positive intercepts and positive gradients. Such plots point to the existence of two reaction paths for the aquation of the complexes, one independent and other dependent of $[H^+]$ and obeying the following rate law :

$$-dc_t/dt = (k_0 + k_1[H^+]) c_t = k_{obs}c_t \quad \dots (1)$$

where c_t represents the total concentration of the complex and the specific rate constants ' k_0 ' and ' k_1 ' are those corresponding to the uncatalysed and the acid catalysed paths respectively.

The pseudo first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the hydrolysis of the complexes in the presence of varying acid concentrations were fitted to equation (1) with the help of a least squares computer programme which varied k_0 and k_1 and minimised the function

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} [(k_0 + k_1[H^+]_i - k_{obs,i})/\sigma^-(k_{obs,i})]^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

where $\sigma^-(k_{obs,i})$ is the error in the i th rate constant, $k_{obs,i}$ corresponding to the hydrogen ion concentration $[H^+]_i$. The initial values of k_0 and k_1 used in this calculation were obtained from the k_{obs} vs. $[H^+]$ plots (eq. 1). The activation parameters for k_0 and k_1 paths were evaluated with the help of the Eyring equation as usual.

Discussion

The rate constants k_0 and k_1 for the complexes were compared with the corresponding values for other carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes^{2,3,5}. The pK of the carboxylate ligands⁶ has also been compared. It has been proposed⁷ that the rates of spontaneous (uncatalysed) aquation of carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes increase with decreasing pK of the carboxylate ligands. No such correlation between k_0 and pK of the substituted salicylate ligands could be established from the results of the present investigation ; however, the difference in pK of these ligands is rather small. The rate and activation parameters corresponding to k_0 and k_1 for the 5-nitro, and the 3-nitrosalicylate complexes are comparable with those of the corresponding values for the salicylate and phthalato complexes. In contrast, the rate and activation parameters for the 5-sulphosalicylatocobalt (III) complex are comparable to those for the 5-bromo complex. 5-sulpho and 5-bromo-salicylate complexes react slower than the salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex in the uncatalysed path.

A linear relationship between ΔH^* and ΔS^* in the k_0 path for most of the reported carboxylate complexes has been found to hold good and suggests⁶ that a single mechanism operates in the aquation (k_0 path) of such carboxylato-pentaamminecobalt (III) complexes. Since the uncatalysed path of aquation for salicylate, phthalato and some other carboxylato-pentaamminecobalt(III) complexes is reported to involve a rate determining Co-O bond fission^{2,5}, the same mechanism may be visualized for the aquation (k_0 path) of the complexes presently studied.

The acid catalysed path of aquation for some carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes⁷ have been suggested to involve rapid and reversible equilibrium protonation of the carboxylate ligand of the cobalt(III) complex followed by the rate limiting aquation of the protonated species.

TABLE 5—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE UNCATALYSED AND ACID CATALYSED PATHS FOR AQUATION OF $(NH_3)_5CoX^{2+}$

X ⁻	pK	k_0 path 70°			k_1 path 70°			Ref
		$k_0 \cdot 10^4 \text{sec}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^* \text{Kcal/mole}$	$\Delta S^* \text{e.u.}$	$k_1 \cdot 10^4 \text{M}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^* \text{Kcal/mole}$	$\Delta S^* \text{e.u.}$	
$C_6H_4(COOH)COO^-$	3.10	4.84 (±0.22)	29.5 (±2.1)	3.0 (±6.0)	48.6 (±1.3)	23.4 (±1.1)	-10.2 (±3.4)	5
$C_6H_4(OH)COO^-$	2.97	5.49 (±0.34)	38.3 (±4.0)	29.0 (±12)	40.9 (±0.9)	26.9 (±1.0)	-0.6 (±3)	2
$C_6H_4(OH)(SO_3^-)COO^-$	2.86	2.92 (±0.15)	20.5 (±2.3)	-24.0 (±6)	15.5 (±0.3)	29.7 (±0.9)	5.8 (±2.3)	3
$C_6H_4(OH)(5-Br)COO^-$	2.66	3.10 (±0.16)	44.0 (±1.2)	44.5 (±3.5)	18.4 (±0.3)	36.7 (±0.2)	27.1 (±0.7)	
$C_6H_4(OH)(5-NO_2)COO^-$	2.12	5.45 (±0.06)	29.8 (±0.3)	4.2 (±0.7)	10.5 (±0.1)	19.7 (±0.3)	-24.0 (±0.8)	
$C_6H_4(OH)(3-NO_2)COO^-$	1.87	5.43 (±0.06)	36.7 (±0.4)	24.2 (±1.2)	20.3 (±0.2)	18.9 (±0.4)	-25.2 (±1.1)	

Oxygen-18 experiments⁹ and linear free energy correlation¹⁰ have indicated that k_1 (acid-catalysed) path of aquation of oxalatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes involves rate determining Co-O bond breaking process. Moreover the rate vs pK of the carboxylate ligand correlation is also consistent with Co-O bond fission in the acid catalysed path of aquation of H-phthalato⁵ and salicylato complexes and the same mechanism is likely to be operative in the cases of the substituted salicylato pentaammine cobalt(III) complexes presently studied.

Acknowledgements

H. K. P. wishes to express his gratitude to Dr. A. C. Dash, Department of Chemistry, Utkal University and N. K. Mohanty, Lecturer in Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur for valuable discussions and necessary assistance.

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